

DESCRIPTION OF BABUR'S CHARACTERISTICS AS A KING, LEGATE AND HEAD OF THE FAMILY IN "BABUR-THE TIGER" BY HAROLD LAMB

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ABSTRACT

This article provides an in-depth look at Harold Lamb's "Babur -the Tiger". The work is dedicated to the image of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, one of the most famous historical figures, and the article pays special attention to the passages describing the character of Babur. Examples and descriptions of Babur's character as an ordinary human ruler or head of the family are given.

INTRODUCTION

Not only Uzbek literature, but also world writers have created many works of art, science and history dedicated to the image of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, one of the most famous figures in the pages of history. Harold Lamb was also able to re-create Babur's personality in the eyes of students through his work "Babur-the tiger". We can be sure of this once again by analyzing the following passages from the work.

MAIN PART

As a young prince and heir to the throne, Babur sought to receive a good education from a young age, as well as constantly improve his military skills. "Babur-the Tiger" also states as followings: "Although Babur was a disciple of the most skillful warriors and archers in the palace, he did not miss the books. His military training was further enhanced by regular

hunting and his father's military campaigns against the banks of the river. His instructor, who taught him how to fight on horseback, was a trained and skilled soldier who taught him how to behave on horseback during military operations and how to get out of difficult situations. But he was forced to do what he could in battle, and he enjoyed the young prince's success.

Despite being a young ruler who took the throne very early, Zahiriddin was able to draw the right conclusions from difficult situations and make quick decisions. Not to mention the courage of his ancestor Amir Temur in capturing Samarkand, the capital of his empire, three times. Harold Lamb describes the situation as follows: After analyzing the current situation, Babur Mirza came to the right conclusion: he should do his best to march to Samarkand and seize the throne at any

cost. If he wants to be the owner of the throne, it should be the throne of his ancestor Amir Temur. "

Because of his age and experience, Babur was not without flaws. Like everyone else, Zahiriddin had a black and white life. In this play, he skillfully describes how he behaved in such situations: he could, but he could not foresee his failures.

The young king, always interested in the way of life of his people, never allowed their property to be looted and trampled by the military and the aristocracy. Harold Lamb describes how he treated soldiers who seized civilian property during the occupation of Samarkand: "He tried to do so when soldiers looted the goods of traders in the market. One day, Babur Mirza's navkars attacked the traders in the market and confiscated their goods. Upon learning of this, Babur Mirza and Qasim Qavchin immediately ordered the confiscated goods to be returned to their owners. According to him, the confiscated property was returned to its owners by noon the next day, and even until a single thread was passed through the needle hole. The young ruler Babur's measures to return the goods of the plundered merchants to their owners have enhanced the prince's prestige in the eyes of the townspeople."

Despite being a descendant of the aristocracy, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur was able to easily adapt to the conditions of poverty and deprivation. He did not despair in any living conditions, but only moved forward: "With his courage in the hardships he faced in the following years, it is clear that Babur could easily have adapted to his living conditions, for better or for worse."

By reading the following passages from Harold Lamb's work, we can see that Babur's courage, hard work, and zeal for his people were invaluable. It is Babur who gives his companions a place in the cave in the bitter cold winter winds and sits outside in a pile of snow. His navkars knew him as a brave and generous man. Most importantly, those who follow him believe that the star of luck will laugh at him. It gave new titles and positions to serviceable and well-known soldiers. "

Despite his advanced age, Zahiruddin was full of energy until the end of his life. He did his best to help his relatives. His qualities are vividly described in the following passage: "Babur Mirza was forty-two years old when he marched on India. passed with. He was still physically strong, and his pure heart was full of zeal, courage, and creativity. He grabbed two of his navkars by the armpits, walked over the castle wall, and bravely jumped over obstacles along the way. He defended not only himself but also his family members, leaving behind the death of his noble relatives. "

Originally seen by many Indians as a ruthless warlord, Babur was in fact a zealous, generous man who was later recognized by the locals: He was a steadfast, verbally compassionate ruler who knew his honor well. It seems that Babur did a lot of good deeds by distributing the fertile lands taken from those who stood in his way with weapons to the emirs and beys who served him faithfully. "

After conquering the land of India, Babur distributes all the wealth in the palace of Ibrahim Lodi, without repeating the custom of plundering and taking control of all the wealth that was the

tradition of the previous invaders. We can be sure of this by reading the following passage from the play: "The first thing Babur did after capturing the palace of Ibrahim was to distribute the wealth in the treasury that the Sultan had carefully preserved. In doing so, he put an end to the Indian tradition of keeping all wealth in the hands of a single ruler, king, rojami, or ordinary landowner. Bobur's unparalleled generosity had elevated him to an unexpected career. In order to strengthen the army and raise the morale of the soldiers, Babur tried to use every opportunity."

It is well known that Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur wrote about his life and work in his autobiographical work "Boburnoma". Surprisingly, Babur did not try to hide or exaggerate any of the truths in his work. Harold Lamb also expresses his personal opinion about Babur's sincerity: , did not write with such objectivity as hiding the truth, that he fled with all his might to save his life, that he was given to drunkenness to forget his sufferings. He evaluates his behavior and attitudes as objectively as if he were watching from the sidelines. "

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